

WELFARE OF UNORGANIZED WORKERS: PROBLEMS & PROSPECTS

Pinto Vincent*, D'Mello Laveena**

*Freston Knowledge Foundation®, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. E-mail:
Vincentpinto79@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, City
Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India. lavynoronha@gmail.com

Abstract

A large portion of India's workforce falls into the unorganized segment and there is a steady growth in it over years. They are outside the purview of labor legislations and without benefits of social protection and often do not even have a legal status as worker. In spite of such common features, the unorganized/informal sector comprises several heterogeneous groups. The researcher has undertaken this study to find out the effectiveness of certain welfare activities in the unorganized sectors in Udupi District. The study further tries to suggest concrete measures to improve the situation of unorganized workers towards their growth and development through labour welfare measures. The units of population were selected by using simple random sampling method. It comprised of 50 respondents out of which 20 workers selected from fishery, 15 workers from unskilled category and 15 from construction industry according to the number. A descriptive design was used. The study attempts to give a true picture regarding the miserable situation of unorganized workers in terms of their working conditions, remuneration, terms of employment, lack of facilities and amenities. There are some practical difficulties in the administration of welfare measures for this sector due to the complex nature of the sector. However the study recommends that the workers in the unorganized sector can be recognized as a special target group by the government for the implementation of programmes of general welfare in the spheres of housing, education, health and other services. Apart from this all governments must support social security measures by providing necessary budgetary support since this sector suffers from paucity of funds.

Keywords: Unorganized, Unskilled, Fishery, Construction, Welfare, and Workforce

1. INTRODUCTION

The question of labor is of vital significance for any country both from the National and International point of view. Indian labour economy is quite wide and there are three major sectors in our economy namely service sector, agricultural sector and the industrial sector. It is quite evident that there are organized and unorganized workers in all these three sectors. Workers employed in industrial sectors are to some extent organized but their number is quite negligible since majority of employees in the industrial sectors are working in household, construction and beedi industries. Hence we find a huge number of workers in the unorganized sector especially in the service sector namely; shops, commercial

establishments, hotels, transport, education, health, banks, post offices, non government organizations, social welfare centers, market, fishing, domestic employment, security guards etc. According to the National Sample Survey conducted in the year 1999-2000, the total employment in both organized and unorganized sectors in the country was of the order of 397 million. Out of this, around 28 million was in the organized sector and the balance 369 million in the unorganized sector. The number of workforce figure 450 million in 2011 where around 430 million workers are employed in a unorganized sector which is increased consecutively. In this context the researcher attempts to highlight the significance of unorganized sector while trying to confer the major problems faced by the workers of this sector.

2.UNORGANIZED WORKER

Unorganized workers are those who engaged in a variety of occupations or employments, ranging from those forest workers like tribes trying to follow traditional vocations within their traditional habitats, and fishermen who venture out to sea in vulnerable canoes, to those who are working in their homes with software, or assembling parts for a highly sophisticated product. Almost the entire non-agricultural activity in rural India is unorganised. Thus, workers in the unorganised sector include all the workers of the unorganised sector as well as the casual and contract workers in the organised sector who, for one reason or another, have failed to get the benefits of protective legislation or laws on social security. Unorganised sector workers are those who do not have any job security, income security or social security and are therefore extremely vulnerable to exogenous shocks. The National Commission on Labour in India 1966 stated, unorganized labour cannot be identified by a definition but would be described as those workers who have not been able to organize in pursuit of a common objective because of the following constraints – the casual nature of employment, ignorance, illiteracy, small size of establishment per person employed, scattered nature of establishment and superior strength of the employer operating singly or in combination. Hence the basic characteristic of this sector is of the variety, complexity, dimensions and variety of the workforce. Thus the term unorganised labourer refers to workers who are employed without job security, standard wages, fixed hours of work, leaves and holidays, and social security like provident fund and medical benefits. They may be working in traditional sectors like domestic work and agriculture or even in the organized sector as casual workers or contract labourers. They may also be self-employed. They are outside the purview of labour legislations and without benefits of social protection, and often do not even have a legal status as worker. In spite of such common features, the unorganised/informal sector comprises several heterogeneous groups. Ministry of Labour has categorised the unorganised labour force under four groups in terms of occupation, nature of employment, especially distressed categories and service categories.

4.KEY CONCEPTS

Unskilled Workers: Manual workers and a number of other workers in the unorganised sector performing diverse activities are considered unskilled workers. Unskilled workers, who are not employed in the organised sector, come in the category of workers in the unorganised sector. The majority of agricultural workers and construction workers belong to this category. Helper category of jobs in all sectors, the manual workers, roadside workers available for all kind of petty jobs, head load workers/ porters, etc. come under this category.

Fishery: India is one of the major fishing countries, with about 5.4 million tonnes of fish production (both from marine and inland water sources). India ranges first among Commonwealth countries and 7th in the world.

Construction Labour: Construction workers may be broadly classified as skilled and unskilled. Usually, couples are found to be working on the same worksite. Though child labour is prohibited, children are engaged for unskilled jobs. Most of the workers in this sector are employed on a casual basis. Unstable employment/earnings and shifting of workplaces are the basic characteristics of work for construction workers. Women engaged in construction work, are the most exploited. Frequent changes in their work and instability deprive them and their children of primary facilities like health, water, sanitary facilities, education and ration cards. In most cases, safety norms are violated.

3. THE STATUS OF THE UNORGANISED SECTOR

The vast majority of India's labour belongs to the unorganized sector. The facts say that about 93 percent of the Indian labour force belongs to the unorganized sector, which is growing, and that hardly any tangible efforts exist to improve their living conditions are truly alarming. Labour welfare laws have not come to the rescue of the unorganized workers and so far there is no way to organize them to make available the benefits, facilities and protection provided by the labour welfare to the unorganized workers. The scope and coverage of labour legislations is limited to hardly 9.4 percent of the total workforce, who are in the so-called organized sector, as per 1991 census. But remaining 90.6 percent of the persons working in unorganized sectors such as the small and marginal farmers, the landless agricultural labourers, the rural artisans, the handicraft men and women, the fishermen and women, the salt workers, the hamals and the building and construction workers, etc., are deprived of protection under social security legislations of the state. Most of the workers of the unorganized sector come from dalit, tribal, minority and most backward caste communities. Caste, class, ethnicity and gender are fundamentally contributive factors to being a worker in the unorganized sector. The plight of rural working class is more deplorable because they are not educated, ready to migrate, and unorganized totally. However, as far as the agricultural sector is concerned, irrespective of economic class, the share of the unorganized workforce remains flat. Further analysis reveals that the coverage of social security schemes has been extremely sparse among the economically and socially vulnerable sections.

4. THE PROBLEM

Over the years, the status of unorganized labour in the country has been studied by various Commissions and the Study Groups. All these studies have projected the plight of the workers in the unorganized sector and called for substantial measures to improve their protection. Several schemes have been evolved in India through legislation and policies to provide social security to the workers in the unorganized sector. Constitution of India makes special provisions in its various articles. There are several legislations which apply partly to the unorganized sector. The proposal of enactment of a comprehensive legislation for the unorganized sector was discussed during 38th Session of Indian Labour Conference held in the year 2002 at New Delhi. Accordingly, the 'Unorganized Sector Workers Bill, 2003' was drafted. It successively drafted another, i.e., the unorganized Workers (Conditions of work) Bill, 2005. The proposed legislation envisaged to regulate the employment and conditions of

service of the unorganized sector workers and to provide for their safety, social security, health and welfare. Lately, the Unorganized Workers Social Security Act, 2008 has been enacted by the Government to provide social security to workers in the unorganized sector. Taking into consideration the all round growth and progress of workers on account of the various existing, both statutory as well as voluntary, labour welfare measures there arise the following pertinent questions. Since most of the welfare legislations cater to workers in organized sectors, how far the unorganized workers have benefited from such labour welfare measures? Has labour welfare so far led to the development of labourers or just met their daily necessities of life? Whether social welfare measures are effective in administering them to the workers of unorganized sector? In this connection the researcher aims to undertake a study on the effectiveness of certain welfare activities in the unorganized sectors in Udupi District. The study further tries to suggest concrete measures to improve the situation of unorganized workers towards their growth and development through labour welfare measures.

5. OBJECTIVES

The study is undertaken with the following objectives.

- To prepare a socio-demographic profile of workers of unorganized sector in Udupi District of Karnataka State.
- To assess the socio-economic status of the respondents.
- To diagnose the work related problems of unorganized workers.
- To identify welfare measures available to unorganized employees and to gather their opinions about the effectiveness of the same.
- To arrive at some concrete and practical measures to improve the socio economic conditions of unorganized employees and elicit their suggestions regarding the same.

6. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The universe of the present study constitutes unorganized workers of different categories, i.e., Fishery, Unskilled Workers and Construction Workers in the regions of Coastal Karnataka. The selected population was measured under simple random sampling method. It comprised of 50 respondents out of which 20 workers selected from fishery, 15 workers from unskilled category and 15 from construction industry according to the number. The respondents were explained the purpose of the study and ensured confidentiality of the data. The researcher used three methods of data collection in order to gather information both from respondents and other informants which consisted of personal interviews, discussions and observation. The study used a descriptive research design. For systematic processing of data the researcher made use of both manual and mechanical system of data processing. Hence the data collected was coded, tabulated and analyzed by the application of logical and statistical reasoning.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-demographic data showed that 40 percent of the respondents were in the age group of 35-45 years, 80 percent were female employees where as 20 percent of them were male employees. The marital status of the respondents revealed that 64 percent of the respondents

were married. Distribution of the religious affiliation shows that majority of them are Hindus (58%) and the rest forming the minority. Majority (86 percent) of the respondents were from rural background. The educational status of the respondents reveals that 86 percent of the respondents were below high school. With regard to the mode of employment of the workers a majority of 54 percent is casual workers and 42 percent are contract workers respectively.

Table No: 1 Family Income of the Respondents

Family Income per month (in Rupees)	Number of Respondents	Total
Upto 5,000	7	14%
5,001-10,000	30	60%
10,001- 15,000	8	16%
15,001 and above	5	10%
Total	50	100%

It is evident from the above table that majority (60 percent) of the respondents' monthly family income distribution is between Rs. 5,001 –Rs. 10,000 per month. Among the other respondents, a considerable percent of respondents fall below Rs. 5000(14 percent) and 16 percent of them are having a monthly family income of Rs. 10,001/- to Rs. 15,000/- per month. There are 10 percent of the respondents earn an income of more than Rs. 15,001/- per month. From the above analysis, we can depict the economic situation of workers in unorganized sector. Since a large number of respondents earn within the category of Rs. 5001-Rs. 10,000 it draws our attention towards the present standard of life in comparison with the income. The living is become very expensive and it is very difficult to maintain a family with scanty financial resources. Also, 10 percent of respondents are very poor since they earn below 5,000. Hence a large (70%) group of respondents live below the poverty line in the unorganized sector.

Table No: 2 Categories of Unorganised Workers V/S Effectiveness of Welfare Measures

Occupation of Workers	Assessment of Problems & Areas of Welfare Suggested									
	Good working environment & Safety practices		Attractive Compensation packages		Availability of job on regular basis		Minimum working hours, Rest and Leisure		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Fisheries	3	6%	5	10%	2	4%	10	20%	20	40%
Construction Workers	2	4%	4	8%	3	6%	6	12%	15	30%

Unskilled workers	4	8%	3	6%	3	6%	5	10%	15 30%
Total	9	18%	12	24%	8	16%	21	42%	50 100%

The table depicts that out of total respondents 40 percent of them belong to the work category of Fishery, 30 percent each from construction & unskilled category respectively.

According to the section on assessment of problems & areas of suggested welfare, the respondents demonstrated higher scores of 42 percent in the domain of minimum working hours, rest and leisure. Here, the vast majority of respondents do not find their work hard on account of the above said problems. Among the other respondents, 24 percent are happy with the compensation package being offered and this is a sizeable percentage where respondents are able to manage with the package that is offered to them. However, there are two other areas of problems are grave because quite a small percent of respondents are satisfied with the facilities while it is a problem for others. The distribution of the same spreads as 9 percent in the case of healthy working environment and safety practices and 8 percent with the job offered on a regular basis.

From the above, we can draw the major problems being faced by the workers in the unorganized sector are: 1. Seasonal employment 2. Unhealthy Work Environment and less safety 3. Low compensation package 4. Lack of regulation in working hours, rest and leisure provided. While two of the former problems are experienced by a large number of respondents, the latter areas are taken care in many of the establishments. Hence the major trouble faced by the unorganized sector is non-availability of work throughout the year. Further, out of 40 percent respondents in the category of fishery only 4 percent are getting employment on a regular basis. Similarly merely 6 percent each receive employment on habitual basis in construction and unskilled category respectively. The second major hitch that we have in this sector is unhealthy working environment, insanitary conditions, lack of security systems, and pollution control, devices which cause great health hazards to workers. Supplementary to this barely 6 percent respondents are pleased with the provisions among 40 percent in Fishery while 4 percent in construction (out of 30 percent) and 8 percent in unskilled (out of 30 percent) category respectively. The next concern for the unorganized workers being the compensation package, opinions slightly differ. There is a considerable percent of respondents(10 percent) are contented with the package offered in Fishery while others still feel it is a smaller amount of the package. Likewise 8 percent in construction and 6 percent in unskilled category among 30 percent of respondents each. This varied distribution may be based on the socio-economic status of the respondents. In the same way, there are equal respondents (20 percent out of 40 percent) express a positive feeling about the minimum working hours, rest and leisure. Also 12 percent respondents in construction and 10 percent in unskilled category get leisure and rest sufficiently. This shows that the problem of working hours does not affect the unorganized workers as much as other problems.

8. IMPLICATIONS AND SUGGESTION

The study is significant in the following ways. It attempts to give a true picture regarding the miserable situation of unorganized workers in terms of their working conditions, remuneration, terms of employment, lack of facilities and amenities. In this way it will bring to light the vast gap in the distribution of income and fair treatment of workers between a

small group of organized employees and a large majority of unorganized workers. The study is an eye opener to the government officials in the ministry of labour and the Non Governmental as well as voluntary agencies working for the betterment of workers to pay immediate attention and initiate swift action in order to work out some efficient and effective measures to improve the conditions of the unorganized employees. Despite of the fact that provision of social security to unorganised sector workers assumed unprecedented significance in the development discourse of India in recent times, it not only fails to cover all the categories of unorganized workers but also in the effective administration of the same. Hence an attempt should be made to rethink the existing social security measures in order to discuss the scope for designing more effective measures as well as machineries to implement these measures.

General suggestions

- There are some practical difficulties in the administration of welfare measures for this sector due to the complex nature of the sector. However, workers in unorganized sector can be recognized as a special target group by the government for the implementation of programmes of general welfare in the spheres of housing, education, health and other services. Apart from this all governments must support social security measures by providing necessary budgetary support since this sector suffers from paucity of funds.
- Though the government is very much concerned to make labour welfare measures available to unorganized workers and introduced several schemes but these has not been implemented in letter and spirit for lack of adequate supervision. Hence, collaboration with various agencies of the government like Panchayats, Nagarapalikas, Department of Social Justice Welfare, NGOs and social workers, etc. will be effective.
- There is no trade union or institutional machinery to represent workers. Unless they are organized and made aware of their strength in unity the dreams of development might remain plat.
- The establishment of more and more institutions of mutual benefit for self employed workers will support the cause very much.

Specific Suggestions

- The major trouble faced by the unorganized sector is non-availability of work throughout the year. The employers should take the responsibility of dispensing them with other occupations so that the employer not only builds a long term relationship with the worker but also continuity with the worker ensures optimum productivity, efficiency and effectiveness. Secondly stock of raw materials can further provide few more months of employment to the workers. Thirdly, the government should support these workers by providing social assistance to undertake self employment in the stop gap period.
- The unorganized sectors continue to suffer from unhygienic and insanitary conditions, lack of security systems, and pollution control, devices which cause great health hazards to workers. So welfare funds need to be augmented to provide maximum welfare services to workers in proportion to their number. The number of welfare

centers in each state also needs to be increased and located near the working place to enable the workers and their families to make their maximum use.

- As mentioned earlier, social assistance by the government and budgetary support will improve the financial situation to provide a good compensation package to the workers. It is also suggested that employers as well as government should promote direct marketing facility to the products of the unorganized sector. This would maximize the profit and in turn benefit the employers as well as employees.

9.CONCLUSION

India's workforce comprises nearly 93 per cent of unorganized workers, with virtually the entire farm sector falling under the informal category, only one-fifth of the non-farm workers are found in the organised segment which is growing, and that hardly any tangible efforts exist to improve the living conditions of these unorganized workers are truly alarming. Though the government has shown interest to make labour welfare measures available to unorganized workers and introduced several schemes these have not been implemented in letter and spirit for lack of adequate supervision and administration. This legislation needs to be an enabling one that will improve livelihood opportunities, provide a decent life to the workers and integrate them with the growing opportunities in the country. Together with the government it is the employers and Trade Unions also have the obligation to contribute to the welfare of the workers for their health and safety through the implementation of different legislations by taking up the activities falling within their purview and sphere.

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